

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-10-IA-1% 05 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	14	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 10
Injection Volume:	20.00 ul	Channel Name:	283.3nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 283.3 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	2/13/2023 21:47:35 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:40:42 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	23.361	30409432	42.01	701493
2	29.377	5591079	7.72	125914
3	31.570	31076307	42.93	606424
4	35.278	5313233	7.34	105152

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-1-IA-1% 05 asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230214
Vial:	14	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	283.3nm
Run Time:	40.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 283.3 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	2/14/2023 9:36:26 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:33:43 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	21.969	486	0.00	-50
2	28.510	179415	0.82	5532
3	29.885	21712512	99.08	581324
4	33.005	22050	0.10	890